

Supplemental Material

Supplementary Methods

Component labelling and artefact identification

The epoched data, which was merged across all testing blocks, was then classified into brain or artefactual components using a semi-automated approach. Data were first automatically labelled as artefacts using SASICA plugin (Chaumon et al., 2015), which also utilises FASTER and ADJUST automated artefact rejection methods (Mognon et al., 2011; Nolan et al., 2010). SASICA identifies artefactual components based on highly focal components (automated thresholding), focal trial activity (automated thresholding), dipole variance ($>15\%$), and EOG artefacts based on correlation ($r > 0.4$) of a component with horizontal eye movements (correlations with F9 and F10 channels) or with blinks (correlations with FP1 and FP2 channels). After the automated classification, component properties were further visually inspected, which included evaluation of dipole variance, scalp maps, PSD plot, ERPs (event-related potentials), ERP image plots, and component time series. Additionally, the automated labels of independent components assigned by ICLabel EEGLAB plugin (<https://github.com/scen/ICLabel>) were compared with SASICA labels. Based on the component properties, and the labels assigned by SASICA and ICLabel, the artefactual components were confirmed and labelled for rejection.

Notably, we ensured that any component activity originating from frontopolar electrodes (as visible on scalp maps) was adequately inspected to ensure that vestibular ocular reflex was identified and labelled as an artefact for removal.

Supplementary Figure S1

Figure S1. Topographic maps showing alpha- and beta-frequency changes for all electrodes in late acceleration (550-950 ms) and late deceleration (1550-1950 ms) phase for healthy and BVP-residual (BVP-R). BVP-complete (BVP-C) maps averaged across whole trial (0-2000 ms). Alpha (8-13 Hz): Despite the visually observed differences there were no statistical differences between

healthy and BVP-residual. Alpha desynchronisation over frontoparietal electrodes was observed in both, healthy and BVP-residual, magnitude of which was relatively larger for healthy during deceleration and for BVP-residual during the acceleration phases. BVP-complete also showed frontoparietal alpha desynchronisation with even magnitude higher than both, healthy and BVP-residual. **Beta desynchronisation:** Despite the clear absence of beta desynchronisation in healthy individuals, there were no statistical differences between healthy, and BVP-residual. BVP-residual patients showed beta desynchronisation primarily over the parietal electrodes. BVP-complete also showed beta desynchronisation over the frontocentral electrodes in addition to the parietal electrodes. (*BVP-residual/BVP-R: bilateral vestibulopathy patients with residual vestibular function; BVP-complete/BVP-C: a single BVP patient with bilaterally transected audio-vestibular nerves; Figure scaled to ± 1 dB, and those marked “*” were scaled to ± 1.5 dB, to ensure consistency for visual comparison across conditions. Scaling was increased to ± 1.5 dB for maps where baseline magnitude across all electrodes appeared to be $> \pm 1$ dB, to reduce difficulty in identifying the origin of activity.*)

Topographic maps for alpha- and beta-frequencies

Topographic maps (representative of all 32 channels) are presented here (Figure S1) separately for the late acceleration (550-950 ms) and late deceleration (1550-1950 ms) phases, to focus on the induced activity and avoid the time-locked broadband frequency changes (Figures 2 & 3). Given that there were no such time-locked changes in the patient without the audio-vestibular nerve (BVP-complete), as shown in Figures 2 & 3, we averaged their data for the whole trial duration for BVP-complete, i.e. 0-2 s.

Alpha desynchronisation

Alpha (8-13 Hz) desynchronisation was observed in both, healthy and BVP-residual, during acceleration as well as deceleration (Figure S1). Overall, there were no statistical differences, however, the magnitude of desynchronisation appeared higher in BVP-residual during acceleration, and for healthy individuals during deceleration (*Figure S1: note the “*” labelled maps that were scaled to ± 1.5 dB*). Notably, this alpha desynchronisation was largely localised over frontoparietal electrodes, without any clearly observable hemispheric differences. The patient without the audio-vestibular nerve (BVP-complete) also had a similar pattern, i.e. frontoparietal alpha desynchronisation, the magnitude of which visually appeared higher than both, healthy and BVP-residual.

Beta desynchronisation

While there were no statistical differences between healthy and BVP-residual, beta desynchronisation was largely absent in healthy individuals for both, acceleration and deceleration (Figure S1). BVP-residual patients showed beta desynchronisation largely localised over parietal electrodes. BVP-complete patient also showed beta desynchronisation over the frontocentral electrodes in addition to the parietal electrodes.

Supplementary Figure S2

Figure S2. Time frequency changes at Cz electrode – comparing the first 2 testing blocks of healthy with 2 blocks of BVP patients. No statistical differences were present, and alpha suppression in healthy appeared marginally higher in deceleration phase, when compared to averaging 5 blocks (Figure 2).

Supplementary Figure S3

Figure S3. Time frequency changes at Pz electrode – comparing 2 first 2 testing blocks of healthy with 2 blocks of BVP patients. No statistical differences or qualitative differences observed. (*BVP-R: BVP-residual group composed of patients with residual peripheral vestibular function; BVP-C: BVP-complete represents a single patients with complete vestibular loss*)

Supplementary Figure S4

Figure S4. Time frequency changes at Cz electrode without artefact removal. Statistical differences observed in beta-gamma range, such as those observed at 150 °/s² at Cz in Figure 2 despite artefact removal. (*BVP-R*: BVP-residual group composed of patients with residual peripheral vestibular function; *BVP-C*: BVP-complete represents a single patients with complete vestibular loss)

Supplementary Figure S5

Figure S5. Patient Variability in vestibular evoked potentials among the BVP-residual patients – demonstrated at highest acceleration level (150 °/s²) . Difference in magnitude of evoked potentials were clearly visible. Some latency differences are also present, such that P300 peaks are relatively delayed for a few patients during acceleration. (black line is mean vestibular evoked potential, and each colour represents individual patient)

Supplementary Figure S6

Figure S6. Comparing vestibular evoked potentials from healthy, BVP-residual and BVP-complete. The N200-P300 complex is visible for BVP-complete patient, even at the lowest acceleration, i.e. 30°/s², however, other components are not clearly identifiable.

Supplementary Figure S7

Figure S7. Inter-trial phase coherence at 'Cz' electrode. Theta increase is visible clearly for healthy and BVP-residual groups. BVP-complete patient also appears to have the theta increase but relatively less prominent.

Supplementary Figure S8

Figure S8. Inter-trial phase coherence at 'Cz' electrode after ERP subtraction. All phase locking in theta increases disappeared after ERP subtraction, demonstrating that theta increase was composed of a phase-locked theta component.

Supplementary Figure S9

Figure S9. Time frequency changes at 'Cz' electrode after ERP subtraction. Theta increases are still observed in healthy and BVP-residual patients despite ERP subtraction, indicating that the time-frequency theta increase contained an induced component of theta increase.

Supplementary Figure S10

Figure S10. Phase amplitude coupling at Cz electrode – demonstrated for highest acceleration (150 °/s²). Inspecting the residual ERP traces after ERP subtraction showed that the phase of low frequency modulated the amplitude of higher frequencies in healthy and BVP-residual. This type of phase-amplitude coupling was completely absent for patient with complete vestibular loss, i.e. BVP-complete. (*blue traces: individual participants; black traces: averaged ERP*)

Figure S11. Vestibular evoked potential for all levels of acceleration. Statistical differences (shaded grey) between healthy and BVP-residual (BVP-R) were observed for $30^\circ/s^2$ between 440-456 ms for 3 samples (*FDR corrected* $p < 0.01$) and from 1952-2140 ms for $120^\circ/s^2$ (*cluster corrected* $p < 0.01$). Inter-subject variability shown via mean \pm S.D. for healthy as light blue and BVP-residual as light red. (*BVP-R: bilateral vestibulopathy patients with residual vestibular function*)